

1 **Title: A Live Experience of Preclinical Studies for ‘Paper of the Future’ with the PRECISE-**
2 **TBI Resources**

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35

36 **Abstract:**

37 The PRE-Clinical Interagency reSearch resourceE-Traumatic Brain Injury (PRECISE-TBI) is a
38 community-based consortium for developing standards, resources, and tools in preclinical studies.
39 The PRECISE-TBI's overarching goal is to bridge the translational gap and accelerate the
40 development of new strategies to prevent and treat patients affected by TBI. The PRECISE-TBI
41 Education Focus Area aims in building relevant TBI resources for blast-related research and works
42 closely with others to provide issues regarding blast injury and outcomes related to the military
43 health community and civilians. We use this focus as an example to systemically test each of the
44 PRECISE-TBI tools to guide development and ensure that they serve user needs. First, we provide
45 a 'use case' illustrating how the PRECISE-TBI minimum viable product (MVP) can be used to
46 support Open Field Blast (OFB) TBI research. PRECISE-TBI resources, including the Model
47 Catalog and the Open Data Commons for TBI (ODC-TBI), represent a researcher-friendly
48 ecosystem specialized for preclinical TBI research to create a truly reusable research environment.
49 We then describe how the PRECISE-TBI MVP can be used to publish the 'Paper of the Future'
50 (PoF) when publishing preclinical TBI studies. The Paper of the Future extends the traditional
51 research article by publishing the step-by-step protocol/workflow at protocols.io and sharing AI-
52 ready original datasets as independent digital objects that adhere to Findable, Accessible,
53 Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles. The use of FAIR practices such as persistent
54 identifiers and rich metadata provides enduring links across the different outputs. These datasets
55 were curated by mapping the community Common Data Elements (CDEs), cross-linking to other
56 relevant publications and research resources for enhanced usability. These studies illustrate an
57 experience demonstrating compliance with the NIH data management & sharing (DMS) mandate,
58 as well as implementing standards and community-vetted best practices to make preclinical TBI
59 data FAIR. Such practices, using next-generation tools, allow us to leverage shared datasets with
60 increased transparency, rigor, and reproducibility to promote reusing the preclinical TBI datasets
61 to identify and evaluate novel target therapies.

62

63 **Keywords:** PRECISE-TBI; Open Field Blast (OFB) model; Open Science; Paper of the Future
64 (PoF); Protocols.io; common data elements (CDEs); AI-ready Tidy data CSV format; Data
65 Management and Sharing (DMS); transparency, rigor and reproducibility; FAIR Principles

66

67 **Introduction**

68 Traumatic brain injury (TBI) is a highly variable clinical condition in terms of injury severity,
69 location, type of damage, and comorbidities (Nortje and Menon 2004; Kline et al. 2016; Manley
70 et al. 2025). The incidence rates of mild TBI (mTBI) are much higher in the military population
71 than those reported for civilians (Chapman and Diaz-Arrastia 2014; Turgoose and Murphy 2018).
72 Low intensity blast (LIB) exposures are among the major causes of mTBIs during military training

73 or in theater deployment (Belmont et al. 2012; Brix et al. 2017; DePalma and Hoffman 2018; Hoge
74 et al. 2008; Owens et al. 2008; Ritenour et al. 2010; Wojcik et al. 2010). Due to such complex and
75 multifaceted medical conditions, translating the results of preclinical studies to bedside therapies
76 for TBI has so far eluded the field. Moreover, among the large volume of publications surveyed in
77 preclinical TBI studies, there is not much sharing of original data, a lack of key information such
78 as resources and devices used, and little standardization on reporting key data elements and entities
79 of the studies (Bandrowski et al. 2026; Ferguson et al. 2014). Over the past decades, neuroscience
80 has strikingly advanced toward open science, moving away from traditional scientific publishing
81 practices. Traditional scientific publications often focus on summarizing research findings in the
82 form of text and figures, with limited emphasis on sharing the underlying primary data or detailed
83 methods, whereas open science takes advantage of advancements in computer science and
84 Artificial Intelligence (AI)-supported bioinformatic tools to expand access to research outputs. It
85 emphasizes transparency, accessibility, and collaboration in the scientific process (Prager et al.
86 2019; Sullivan, DeHaven, and Mellor 2019).

87 Rigor and reproducibility are crucial in research. Several factors, such as lack of access to
88 methodological details and data, complex data management challenges, and poor experimental
89 design, have led to difficulties in reproducing research findings. In January 2023, the NIH updated
90 its Data Management and Sharing (DMS) Policy to require all NIH awardees to submit a DMS
91 plan, [https://grants.nih.gov/policy-and-compliance/policy-topics/sharing-policies/dms/policy-
92 overview](https://grants.nih.gov/policy-and-compliance/policy-topics/sharing-policies/dms/policy-overview) (updated on August 5, 2025). The updated DMS Policy calls for all scientific data to be
93 managed effectively and shared as soon as possible in a manner that makes them Findable,
94 Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable, i.e., FAIR (Wilkinson et al. 2016). As effective data
95 management and data sharing practices are often new to bench scientists, efforts are underway to
96 provide better training and tools (Ferguson et al. 2014; Fouad et al. 2024).

97 Every research lab has its own experimental protocols, and methods for data analysis, and
98 has successfully published their research discoveries. When reading publications, the data
99 collected from different labs vary in format, terminology, and measurement units. These
100 differences make it difficult to compare or combine datasets for FAIR reuse. The lack of
101 standardization can lead to inconsistency, conversion errors, semantic differences, and variability
102 in data quality. The datasets from different labs may not be easily interoperable, making it difficult
103 to harmonize similar data across studies or to integrate data across different modalities. Data
104 transformation requires significant effort and can introduce errors compromising the reliability and
105 validity of the research findings. Lack of access to usable primary data can also lead to duplication
106 of effort and challenges in sharing information across different research groups and institutions.

107 The PREClinical Interagency reSearch resourceE-TBI (PRECISE-TBI) consortium is a multi-
108 institutional team with the mission to support preclinical research community by developing open
109 science resources and approaches to accelerate the development of therapies for TBI by addressing
110 the issues enumerated above (Radabaugh et al. 2023). These resources include the definition of
111 preclinical Common Data Elements (CDEs) (LaPlaca et al. 2021; Smith et al. 2015) to standardize

112 data across studies, a Model Catalog which provides a database of key parameters used within
113 published studies, a set of on-line protocols covering the major pre-clinical TBI models, and the
114 Open Data Commons for Traumatic Brain Injury (ODC-TBI) (Chou et al. 2022), a dedicated open
115 repository for managing and sharing data preclinical TBI data. PRECISE-TBI also is committed
116 to providing training workshops and presentations to aid in the use of these resources.

117 All of these resources lay the foundation for transforming the conduct and publishing of
118 preclinical research to maximize the value of individual research studies for clinical translation.
119 We believe that evolving scientific publishing for advancing science as a global public good (as
120 the International Science Council’s founding strategy) and encouraging open public engagement
121 with science has never been more important to society. By applying these practices, our
122 community has the opportunity to accelerate the development of effective tests and therapies for
123 TBI.

124 In the following, we showcase how resources under development in PRECISE-TBI are
125 informed by and used by researchers, using open field blast (OFB) studies (Chen et al. 2022;
126 Siedhoff et al. 2022) as a use case. Then, using examples from open field blast and closed-head
127 injury studies, we illustrate how these practices and products are brought together to publish the
128 “Paper of the Future” (PoF), increasing transparency and rigor through linking detailed methods
129 and AI-ready datasets to the traditional research article (Box 1).

130

Box 1. What is the Paper of the Future

The Paper of the Future (PoF) is built on two concepts championed by open science: the FAIR data principles (Martone 2015; Wilkinson et al. 2016) and research objects (Bechhofer et al. 2010). The FAIR data principles provide a set of guidelines for ensuring that data is designed to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. Research objects refer to structured digital packages that provide a complete accounting of the inputs and outputs of a research study. Currently, the primary output and the one that is most rewarded and shared is the research paper. But in the course of a study, we use and produce data, code, protocols, tools, reagents, genetically modified organisms, etc. In the PoF, each of these objects are viewed as primary products of research that can be published, cited, tracked and credited independently of the paper itself (Figure 1).

The PoF is therefore more than just the paper: it is a collection of linked research objects, each FAIR and in a form optimized for re-use. Rather than cramming everything into the paper, this structure gives us the opportunity to provide additional, critical detail and host these objects on platforms that are specialized for each type, e.g., a data repository hosts the data, a code repository like GitHub is used to manage code. According to the FAIR principles, each of these research objects is given a unique identifier such as a DOI and is described by a set of rich metadata.

Figure 1. The publication of the future is with PRECISE-TBI resources.

PRECISE-TBI is providing guidelines and tools for the PoF in preclinical TBI research, promoting transparency, reproducibility and AI-readiness. This starts with making sure that the data produced as part of a study are available for reuse by submitting them to a dedicated data repository like the ODC-TBI that supports FAIR. We also recommend that two other products of research, protocols (methodology) and the code that was generated to process or analyze the data, also be shared. We encourage the deposition of a detailed experimental protocol using on-line platforms such as [protocols.io](https://www.protocols.io/) and code into a code-management system such as GitHub. Both platforms are specialized for publishing these research products, and provide handy features such as version control and provenance tracking, as both protocols and code evolve frequently. Finally, PRECISE-TBI recommends that all software tools, reagents, cell lines and genetically modified organisms that are obtained from 3rd party sources are cited using their research resource identifier (RRID) (Bandrowski et al. 2016) to ensure that they are unambiguously identified and easily tracked across studies.

132 Developing and Using PRECISE-TBI Tools for Open Field Blast

133 To help develop the concept of the PoF and the necessary tools, the PRECISE-TBI Education
134 Core, charged with developing resources to improve rigor and reproducibility for blast-related TBI
135 preclinical studies, provided the first use cases. Using previously published studies from our group
136 (Chen et al. 2022; Siedhoff et al. 2022) the original data of the Open Field Blast (OFB) studies
137 underwent mapping to the core CDEs recommended from the PRECISE-TBI, adopting the AI-
138 ready Tidy CSV format required for upload of data into the ODC-TBI. Key metadata from these
139 papers were ingested into the PRECISE Model Catalog, along with a detailed protocol (doi:
140 [dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.yxmvm2kwog3p/v1](https://doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.yxmvm2kwog3p/v1)) deposited into [Protocols.io](https://protocols.io), an online
141 platform for sharing and using scientific protocols. The papers, protocol, and datasets are all
142 connected together in the ODC-TBI and the PRECISE-TBI Model Catalog, which provide links
143 to all three types of the products. In the following, we describe each of these products and their
144 use in detail.

145

146 *The PRECISE-TBI Model Catalog: Synthesis and Planning*

147 The PRECISE-TBI consortium has established a Model Catalog (RRID:SCR_024626;
148 <https://scicrunch.org/precise-tbi/about/model-catalog>) to provide easy searchable ways to compare
149 across the many different model systems used for preclinical TBI research. The Model Catalog
150 takes a knowledge-based approach by developing a taxonomy of preclinical model types to allow
151 easy comparison across the key dimensions of preclinical TBI (Fig 2; Xref Model Catalog and
152 BIKO article). When researchers are designing/choosing a TBI model for a preclinical study,
153 searching the PRECISE-TBI Model Catalog can be a first step. Detailed information of the OFB
154 model in mice, for instance, can be found by clicking on the Model Catalog's landing page, which
155 links here <https://scicrunch.org/precise-tbi/about/model-catalog> (Figure 2).

Welcome to the [PRECISE-TBI model catalog](#)!

The [PRECISE-TBI model catalog](#) is a queryable online resource for preclinical TBI model literature metadata. It aims to enhance the reproducibility of preclinical TBI research by increasing the ability to find and access preclinical TBI model papers. A preclinical investigator expert has identified all papers within the model catalog from a PubMed search. If you know of other papers that should be featured in the PRECISE-TBI model catalog, please let us know by selecting the "Contact help desk" prompt below. The model catalog can be accessed [here](#).

Study	TBI Model Type	Species	Strain	Sex	Age (weeks)	Weight (grams)
Chen CE et al. 1991	Controlled cortical impact model	rat	Springe-Dawley	No sex reported	No age reported	No weight reported
Ji X et al. 2014	Weight-drop model	mouse	ICR	male	No age reported	28 - 32
Myshetskii R et al. 2015	Weight-drop model	rat	Springe-Dawley	male, female	No age reported	No weight reported
Songzei P et al. 2015	Controlled cortical impact model	mouse	C57BL/6	male	No age reported	18 - 20
Xiang L et al. 2018	Weight-drop model	rat	Springe-Dawley	female	No age reported	200 - 250
Adelson PD et al. 2019	Controlled cortical impact model	rat	Springe-Dawley	male	1 - 2.45	15 - 40
Siedhoff R et al. 2021	Controlled cortical impact model	9/9	Yorkshire	female	No age reported	No weight reported

The model catalog currently focuses on the preclinical TBI models listed below. Please click on your model of interest to learn more. Additional models will be added in the future.

- [Fluid percussion injury model](#)
- [Controlled cortical impact model](#)
- [Blast model](#)
- [Weight-drop model](#)

156

157 *Figure 2. Published information on the OFB studies in mice under Blast model (arrow indicated) can be*
 158 *found within the PRECISE-TBI Model Catalog shown in Table format. Retrieved October 20, 2025.*

159 Several commonly used preclinical TBI models are found within the PRECISE-TBI Model
 160 Catalog, including the OFB model. Each model type is curated with standardized protocols to
 161 ensure reproducibility in TBI research. Summaries of all data and protocols available for each
 162 model type can be viewed on the Model Type landing pages, accessible via the Model Catalog
 163 home page (Figure 2) or from the results page. The landing page for the blast model is shown in
 164 Figure 3. This page provides general information about the model type, along with a list of
 165 Publications, associated ODC-TBI datasets (Figure 3), and Protocols. Our publications (Chen et
 166 al. 2022; Siedhoff et al. 2022; Chen, Mei et al. 2018; Chen et al. 2018) associated with the blast
 167 model, among others, can be found here. A link to each publication is also provided via its PMID.
 168 The protocol, "Open-field blast (OFB) model in mice" under Protocols (Figure 3 on the right
 169 column) takes you to a protocol published by Johnson et al. (2023) on protocols.io. Note that even
 170 though the papers were originally published without either an accompanying protocol or datasets,
 171 the links to these products are now provided through the Model Catalog, enhancing the original
 172 paper. As of Aug 12, 2025, the protocol (Johnson et al. 2023) associated with this paper has been
 173 viewed > 1000 times.

TBI Model Type Report

Home / Discovery Sources / ks-precise-tbi-model / Blast model

Blast model

A model of traumatic brain injury occurring in a laboratory that is designed to simulate various aspects of complex blast-induced injury scenarios, including open field exposure, blast tubes using explosives, or shock tubes using compressed air or gas.

Blast model catalog total records: 26 [View All](#)

Synonyms: blast exposure model, blast injury model, blast injury

Model Common Data Element (CDE): In development - available soon

Species: pig, mouse, rat

Assessments: stress relaxation, Fractional Zener constitutive model, fractional Zener constitutive model, unconfined compression test, L/D emergence task, Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), Barnes Maze test test, Contextual fear memory testing, Elevated zero maze, Fear conditioning, Immunohistochemistry (IHC), Light dark escape, Locomotor activity, Novel object localization test, Novel object recognition test, Oligomeric Aβ42 dot blot analysis, Social interaction, Sound-attenuat ...[more]

Releasing Factor Neuronal Activity in the Mouse Hypothalamic Paraventricular NucleusFront Synaptic Neurosci. 2022 Jan 27;13:804898. doi: 10.3389/fnsyn.2021.804898. eCollection 2021. PMC8828487 PMID:35153711

Siedhoff HR, Chen S, Balderrama A, Sun GY, Koopmans B, DePalma RG, Cui J, Gu Z.Long-Term Effects of Low-Intensity Blast Non-Inertial Brain Injury on Anxiety-Like Behaviors in Mice: Home-Cage Monitoring Assessments.Neurotrauma Rep. 2022 Jan 11;3(1):27-38. doi: 10.1089/neur.2021.0063. eCollection 2022. PMID:35141713

Chen S, Siedhoff HR, Zhang H, Liu P, Balderrama A, Li R, Johnson C, Greenleaf CM, Koopmans B, Hoffman T, DePalma RG, Li DP, Cui J, Gu Z.Low-intensity blast induces acute glutamatergic hyperexcitability in mouse hippocampus leading to long-term learning deficits and altered expression of proteins involved in synaptic plasticity and serine protease inhibitors.Neurobiol Dis. 2022 Apr;165:105634. doi: 10.1016/j.nbd.2022.105634. Epub 2022 Jan 22. PMID:35077822

Johnson, C., Cui, J., Zuckerman, A., Song, H., K. Hubler, G., G. DePalma, R., Cernak, I., & Gu, Z. (2022). Open-field blast (OFB) model in mice v1.
<https://doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.yxmvm2kwog3p/v1>
 DOI:10.17504/protocols.io.yxmvm2kwog3p/v1

Zuckerman, A., Siedhoff, H., Balderrama, A., Jiankun Cui, & Gu, Z. (2023). Home-cage monitoring general behavior of C57BL/6J male mice during the CognitionWall test 3 months after open-field LIB exposure (Version 1.0) [Data set]. Open Data Commons for Traumatic Brain Injury (ODC-TBI). <https://doi.org/10.34945/F59W23>
 DOI:10.34945/F59W23

Virginia Tech Advanced Blast Simulator small (RRID:SCR_025395)

Virginia Tech Advanced Blast Simulator large (RRID:SCR_025393)

175

176 *Figure 3. The Blast model page, including general Model Type Information on the top, the Publications*
 177 *using OFB model showed on the left column, whereas the publication of the detailed protocol of the OFB*
 178 *model in mice can be found under Protocols on the right, linking to the Protocols.io website. Additional*
 179 *information includes ODC-TBI data and Devices. The red arrow indicates the link “View All” for available*
 180 *“Blast model catalog total records”, it will direct users to another webpage, which includes more*
 181 *publications on other blast models. Retrieved October 20, 2025.*

182

183 The Model Catalog also provides individual records for each published study, extracting key
184 parameters of the PRECISE-TBI recommended “Core CDEs” such as species, strain, subject
185 characteristics, assessments used and devices. All blast model records can be accessed by clicking
186 on “View all” under the Model Type Information box (Figure 3, arrow).

187 The Model Catalog offers several search and display options. Specific TBI models can be
188 found by entering key words into the “SEARCH” bar. For instance, entering the keywords
189 hyperlinked “[blast model](#)”, will display several publications related to open-field blast (OFB)
190 models. Users can also utilize Facets (Figure 4 left column) to refine their search based on
191 additional parameters such as sex, species and assessments used.

192
193 *Figure 4. The publications related to the Open-field blast model (Chen S. et al., 2022) displayed under*
194 *PRECISE-TBI Model Catalog webpage. It also can be searchable when entering the keywords through the*
195 *“SEARCH” function. The search function can be refined based on the specific criteria under “Facets”.*
196 *Retrieved October 20, 2025.*

197 Each study in the PRECISE-TBI Model Catalog has its own landing page to make it easier to
198 find information linked to that publication, <https://scicrunch.org/precise-tbi/discovery/source/ks-precise-tbi-model/search?q=chen%20S&l=chen%20S&sources=ks-precise-tbi-model>. Using one
199 of our publications (Figure 4) as an example, the detailed information can be accessed on the
200 landing page via two tabs (Figure 5), INFORMATION and TOOLS AND RESOURCES.
201

202 The tab “INFORMATION” contains the essential curated information, including TBI Model,
203 TBI model parameters, Animal Information, and Assessments.

Login Register

PRECISE-TBI ABOUT ▾

Chen S. et al.,2022

Home / Discovery Sources / ks-precise-tbi-model / [Chen S. et al.,2022](#)

Low-intensity blast induces acute glutamatergic hyperexcitability in mouse hippocampus leading to long-term learning deficits and altered expression of proteins involved in synaptic plasticity and serine protease inhibitors.

S Chen | HR Siedhoff | H Zhang | P Liu | A Balderrama | R Li | C Johnson | CM Greenlief | B Koopmans | T Hoffman | RG DePalma | DP Li | J Cui | Z Gu
Neurobiology of disease | 2022 Apr
[PubMed](#)

Neurocognitive consequences of blast-induced traumatic brain injury (bTBI) pose significant concerns for military service members and veterans with the majority of "invisible injury." However, the underlying mechanism of such mild bTBI by low-intensity blast (LIB) exposure for long-term cognitive and mental deficits remains elusive. Our previous studies have shown that mice exposed to LIB result in nanoscale ultrastructural abnormalities in the absence of gross or apparent cellular dama ...[more]

Pubmed ID: 35077822 [RIS Download](#)

INFORMATION **TOOLS AND RESOURCES**

<p>Device Name</p> <p>No information available</p>	<p>Associated Datasets</p> <p>DOI:10.34945/F59W23</p>	<p>Associated Protocols</p> <p>DOI:10.17504/protocols.io.yxmv2kwog3pv1</p>
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204

205 *Figure 5. Additional information associated with the publication of Chen S. et al., 2022 provides the links*
 206 *to the Associated Datasets and Protocols pages, respectively under the TOOLS AND RESOURCES tab.*
 207 *Retrieved October 20, 2025.*

208

209 Under the TOOLS AND RESOURCES tab, the original datasets, deposited at the Open Data
 210 Commons for Traumatic Brain Injury (ODC-TBI), for multi-phase home-cage behavioral testing
 211 related to each original publication using the OFB model of mild TBI, are listed (Figure 7B). The
 212 ODC-TBI datasets are also accessible via the Blast model page (as ODC-TBI Data in Figure 7A),
 213 located underneath Publications in Figure 3, under “Associated Datasets.”

214 The individual behavioral assessments with their original study datasets in ZIP and CSV format
 215 (DOI: [10.34945/F59W23](https://doi.org/10.34945/F59W23), e.g., <https://odc-tbi.org/data/872>, accession # 872) (Figure 7B) were
 216 deposited at the ODC-TBI repository platform (RRID:SCR_021736). More details about the
 217 ODC-TBI platform are provided below.

218

219

220 **[Protocols.io: Standardized Protocols for Blast TBI](#)**

221 In addition to making details of the research methods available and searchable via the Model
 222 Catalog, this resource also provides the toolkit that can help researchers design new, standardized

223 protocols (<https://scicrunch.org/precise-tbi/about/tbi-protocols>). This effort will improve rigor and
224 reproducibility by reducing the variability of model usage between laboratories to enhance
225 translation studies (Xref. Floyd, Gurkoff, et al. PRECISE-TBI Mission article). Providing a step-
226 by-step protocol is crucial for reproducibility between labs and within the same lab by different
227 lab members over time. Under the right column of Figure 3, the OFB model protocol, accessible
228 via the provided link on protocols.io and associated with this publication, provides more
229 experimental details than the methods section of the published research articles (Figure 6; DOI:
230 [10.17504/protocols.io.yxmvm2kwog3p/v1](https://doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.yxmvm2kwog3p/v1)).

231 Under the *Steps* tab, it consists of Disclaimer (provided with the contact information
232 VHACMOOFBC@va.gov) and the following sections: Animal Preparation; the procedures for
233 OFB Setup; Induction of Primary Blast Injury conditions; and Induction of Sham Injury. All
234 training and approvals should be in place before the use of explosives. The list of references for
235 the protocol is presented as a PDF in the attachment.

The screenshot shows the protocols.io website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with a menu icon, the protocols.io logo, a search bar, and 'SIGN IN' and 'SIGN UP' buttons. Below the navigation bar, the date 'Jan 23, 2023' is displayed. The main content area features the title 'Open-field blast (OFB) model in mice' with a red arrow pointing to it from the text 'Title, DOI, Authors, etc.'. Below the title, the DOI 'dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.yxmvm2kwog3p/v1' is listed, followed by the authors: Catherine Johnson^{1,2,3}, Jiankun Cui^{4,1,3}, Amitai Zuckerman^{4,3,1}, Hailong Song⁴, Graham K. Hubler⁴, Ralph G. DePalma^{5,6}, Ibolja Cernak⁷, and Zezong Gu^{4,3,1}. Below the authors, there are footnotes for each institution: ¹Open Field Blast Core; ²Missouri University of Science and Technology, Department of Mining and Explosives Engineering, Rolla, MO 65409, USA; ³PRECISE-TBI; ⁴Department of Pathology and Anatomical Sciences, University of Missouri – Columbia School of Medicine, Columbia, MO 65211, USA; ⁵Norman Rich Department of Surgery, Uniformed University of Health Sciences, Bethesda, MD 20814; ⁶Office of Research and Development, Department of Veterans Affairs, Washington, DC 20420, USA; ⁷Department of Biomedical Sciences, Mercer University School of Medicine, Columbus, GA 31901, USA. At the bottom of the page, there are tabs for 'PRECISE-TBI', 'Steps', 'Metadata', 'Materials', and 'Metrics'. The 'Disclaimer' section is visible, containing text about the approval of methods and the use of explosives.

236
237 *Figure 6. The detailed experimental protocol of the OFB model in mice published at the Protocols.io*
238 *repository with DOI issued as a standing alone publication. Retrieved October 20, 2025.*

239 The detailed protocol enhances transparency and helps maintain consistency across different
240 studies (Xref Floyd, Gurkoff, et al. PRECISE-TBI Mission article thru improving rigor,
241 reproducibility, and transparency). Other researchers can accurately replicate the study, which is
242 essential for verifying the results and building on previous work. An important feature of
243 protocols.io, familiar to researchers who manage code, is the ability to “fork” protocols, making a

244 copy that can be modified for their own study. Unlike simply copying a protocol, forking retains
245 the provenance to the original, allowing easy tracking of any changes as the protocol is modified.

246 Under the Protocol *Metadata* tab, multiple helpful pieces of information
247 are listed, including DOI, links to PDF and HTML formats of the protocol,
248 protocol and reference citations, protocol status, and keywords; It also includes
249 the license. Both Widgets and QR codes are provided for different user
250 preferences and scenarios. The *Materials* tab includes a list of detailed
251 Equipment and Materials; these will ensure the other researchers can
252 accurately replicate the experiment for verifying results and building on
253 previous works. RRIDs are included for specific materials and equipment to properly identify the
254 exact materials used by the researchers (Bandrowski and Martone 2016; Jackson, Chen, Nguyen,
255 et al. 2024). The *Metrics* tab reveals activities of the website visits over time, tracking views and
256 downloads. The DOI allows users to cite protocols in research articles, and these citations are
257 tracked by publishers (Jackson, Chen, Liu, et al. 2024) (e.g.,
258 <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00193-024-01169-2>).

259

260

261 [ODC-TBI.org](https://odc-tbi.org): Community platform for sharing AI-Ready OFB data

262

263 *Figure 7. Illustration of ODC-TBI:872 dataset description on phenotypic studies. (A) Additional component*
 264 *of the TBI Model Type Report page on Blast model in Figure 3 — “ODC-TBI Data.” (B) The metadata of*
 265 *the home-cage monitoring (HCM) behavioral assessments of C57BL/6J male mice by the CognitionWall*
 266 *test (DOI:10.34945/F59W23). Retrieved October 20, 2025.*

267 Within ODC-TBI, public datasets (Figures 7B and 8) are accompanied by 1) a description,
 268 including title, citation, abstract, and etc.; 2) Dataset and related materials, including “Full Data
 269 Package” (ZIP) and Data Dictionary (CSV); 3) Links to publications, protocols and other
 270 associated items. In this page (Figure 8), users can obtain additional information, such as animal
 271 housing, handling, and weather conditions that may affect the experiment. Note that downloading
 272 the full data package from this page requires an account, which can be obtained through a simple
 273 registration. The Full Data Package (ZIP) and CSV files contain subject level data and metadata,
 274 and a metadata dictionary that describes the meaning and structure of each variable contained in
 275 the dataset.

276

277 *Figure 8. Additional information from the ODC-TBI:872. (A) PROVENANCE / ORIGINATING*
 278 *PUBLICATIONS for the cross-linked original publication, and other links under RELEVANT LINKS. (B)*
 279 *The linked ODC-TBI dataset of the home-cage monitoring spontaneous activity. (C) Open-Field Blast*
 280 *physical parameters datasets (Data Gu Lab_2019_2020) tracking each animal during OFB exposure.*
 281 *Retrieved October 20, 2025.*

282 In the dataset (Figure 8A), <https://odc-tbi.org/data/872> (DOI: [10.34945/F59W23](https://doi.org/10.34945/F59W23)), under
 283 PROVENANCE / ORIGINATING PUBLICATIONS are provided cross-links to the original
 284 publication (Chen et al. 2022) that enhances the credibility of the publication. Through the
 285 RELEVANT LINKS, the OFB model protocol and additional ODC-TBI datasets related to the
 286 publication can be easily accessed via a unique digital object identifier (DOI).

287 Relevant links can also include links to related datasets. For the above dataset (Accession #
 288 872), the first linked ODC-TBI dataset, titled "Home-cage monitoring (HCM) spontaneous activity
 289 of C57BL/6J male mice 3 months after open-field low-intensity blast exposure," represents our
 290 dataset of ODC-TBI Accession:871. It is also associated with the same publication (Figure 5) and
 291 provides another neurological phenotype test in HCM, spontaneous activity (Figure 8B). The
 292 second linked ODC dataset, titled "Open-field Blast parameters dataset" (highlighted in Figure
 293 8C) represents another dataset of ODC-TBI Accession:882. Through the link, it directs users to
 294 the detailed file "Open Field Blast (OFB) Data Gu Lab_2019_2020" (Figure 8C) of the
 295 accompanied blast physical parameters tracked in each batch of animals during blast exposure
 296 ("Open Field Blast (OFB) Data Gu Lab_2019_2020") (Figure 8C), and this file is also available
 297 at <http://dx.doi.org/10.34945/F5630G>. It is associated with the same publication.

298 Clicking on the “ZIP” link for ODC-TBI Public Dataset ODC-TBI:872
299 (<http://doi.org/10.34945/F59W23>) downloads the data as a .zip file in CSV and associated data
300 dictionary file. It is one of the original raw datasets of Home-cage monitoring (HCM) general
301 behavior of C57BL/6J male mice during the CognitionWall test 3 months after open-field LIB
302 exposure (Figure 9). Due to the extensive volume of data, only a portion of the dataset is shown in
303 Figure 9, making it easier to identify the individual items. Users can view and download the full
304 dataset by logging in. In this study, the locomotor activity of the mice was measured using the
305 PhenoTyper® home-cages and CognitionWall™ system with the EthoVision software (Noldus
306 Information Technology, The Netherlands). The program-acquired data were uploaded to the web-
307 based AHCODA-DB (Sylics, Bilthoven, The Netherlands) for meta-analysis and obtained the
308 original readable raw data (Figure 9A).

309 Environmental conditions can significantly impact the effects of OFB TBI. Variations in
310 atmospheric pressure and weather conditions, such as humidity and temperature, can influence the
311 propagation of blast waves. For instance, higher humidity can increase the density of the air,
312 potentially amplifying the blast wave's impact on the brain. Those conditions have been reported
313 in the dataset (Accession # 882; Figure 8C). The OFB measurement dataset of the C4 detonation
314 parameters are associated with the ODC-TBI Accession # 871 and 872 datasets, which capture
315 behavior outcomes. Integrating linkage of multiple datasets allows users to efficiently track
316 individual animal subjects and accurately assess specific animal outcomes. These physical
317 measurements and conditions are vital in providing essential datasets for further investigation on
318 OFB TBI severity.

319 The datasets of ODC-TBI (Accession:871, 872, and 882) were collected from the same
320 subjects across multiple studies that examined HCM neurological phenotypes in these mice 3
321 months after blast injury and blast physical monitoring during OFB exposure. The OFB-TBI had
322 been performed using the identical protocol. Those datasets and the protocol support findings in
323 the publication, [doi: 10.1016/j.nbd.2022.105634](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbd.2022.105634) (Chen et al. 2022). These comprehensive, multi-
324 component datasets are interoperable and reuseable in AI-ready Tidy CSV format, as valuable
325 resources of the preclinical TBI studies, in supporting the creation of a more data and knowledge
326 severity score by the PRECISE-TBI community (Xref. Ferguson et al. PRECISE-TBI Injury
327 Severity Index article). Because of good data management practices, the datasets could be
328 published well after the paper was published (Xref Martone, Ferguson, et al. ODC-TBI DMS
329 article). This transparency enhances accessibility, helps demystify the research process and fosters
330 trust in scientific findings.

331 Study-level metadata are collected from device/equipment with the critical details to
332 understand the overall design in the study. For preparing such original raw metadata in Tidy data
333 format (Figure 9), each column represents a study parameter, outcome measure, field or variable
334 (Fouad et al. 2024; Huie et al. 2021; Wickham 2014). The first row of the dataset contains the
335 parameter names in each column. In the following, each row represents a single observation for a
336 single subject. A subject could have multiple rows. For example, the open field dataset in our study

337 (data not shown, should be coming soon on PRECISE-TBI website) included multiple time points
 338 for each subject (like 3 DPI, 6 DPI, segmented by 1 min etc.), in which case each row might
 339 represent a unique observation of a subject/animal at a specific time point. The Subject ID column
 340 will help identify all the data for each specific subject in the dataset and link to the other dataset
 341 containing the OFB physical variables of the blast overpressure parameters.

342
 343 *Figure 9. The original raw dataset for the ODC-TBI:872 dataset in Tidy data format using the ODC-TBI*
 344 *toolkit for mapping the core metadata elements recommended by the PRECISE-TBI along with other unique*
 345 *metadata elements of the PhenoTyper home-cage monitoring assessments. Retrieved October 20, 2025.*

346 Different software or labs may use different parameter names to present individual data
 347 elements. For easier data sharing and integration across different studies and organizations, we
 348 need the data dictionary to ensure data is collected and described consistently across different
 349 labs/software, making it easy to compare and combine datasets. It also provides clear definitions
 350 for each data element and helps researchers understand precisely what each variable represents
 351 and how it was measured (Figure 10).

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	VariableName	Title	Unit of Measure	Description	DataType	PermittedValues	MinimumValue	MaximumValue	Comments
2	Subject	Unique identification of each mouse ID		Unique identification of each mouse ID	Numeric		VA-V-01	VA-V-99	
3	Species	Species of the mouse		Species of the mouse	Alphanumeric	Multiple			
4	Strain	Strain of the mouse		Strain of the mouse	Alphanumeric	Multiple			
5	Sex	Sex of the mouse		Sex of the mouse	Alphanumeric	Female; Male			
6	Group	Exposure group		The exposure group assignment for each mouse.	Alphanumeric	Sham; Blast			
7	time	Time of the test in hours	hours	Time of the test in hours, for example 1 is 1st hour, 2 2nd, etc.	(Numeric		1	95	The test started at 4:3
8	Average distance moved per moving segment	Average distance moved per moving segment	cm	Average distance moved per moving segment	Numeric				
9	Average maximum acceleration	Average maximum acceleration	cm/s ²	Average maximum acceleration	Numeric				
10	Average maximum velocity	Average maximum velocity	cm/s	Average maximum velocity	Numeric				
11	Average size of arrest segments	Average size of arrest segments	Seconds	Average size of arrest segments	Numeric				
12	Average size of moving segments	Average size of moving segments	Seconds	Average size of moving segments	Numeric				
13	Average size of shelter segments	Average size of shelter segments	Seconds	Average size of shelter segments	Numeric				
14	Distance moved	Distance moved	cm	Distance moved	Numeric				
15	Maximum acceleration	Maximum acceleration	cm/s ²	Maximum acceleration	Numeric				
16	Number of arrest segments	Number of arrest segments	Frequency	Number of arrest segments	Numeric				
17	Number of moving segments	Number of moving segments	Frequency	Number of moving segments	Numeric				
18	Number of shelter entrances	Number of shelter entrances	Frequency	Number of shelter entrances	Numeric				
19	Number of shelter exits	Number of shelter exits	Frequency	Number of shelter exits	Numeric				
20	Number of shelter segments	Number of shelter segments	Frequency	Number of shelter segments	Numeric				
21	Time moving	Time moving	Seconds	Time moving	Numeric				
22	Total time arrest	Total time arrest	Seconds	Total time arrest	Numeric				
23	Total time in shelter	Total time in shelter	Seconds	Total time in shelter	Numeric				
24	Total time outside	Total time outside	Seconds	Total time outside	Numeric				
25	Total time sleep outside	Total time sleep outside	Seconds	Total time sleep outside	Numeric				

352
 353 *Figure 10. The metadata dictionary of the ODC-TBI:872 dataset in CSV format can be*
 354 *downloaded from the ODC-TBI.org. Retrieved October 20, 2025.*

355 *Common Data Elements: Mapping Core CDEs and Metadata Recommended from*
356 *PRECISE-TBI*

357 CDEs (Figure 11) provide a standardized set of
358 data elements allowing semantic interoperability for
359 better data management and better science. They
360 streamline protocol standardization and data
361 collection processes and ensure that all acquired data
362 are described in the same way. Their use ensures
363 their data is compatible with other datasets. Along
364 with their definitions, formats, and permissible
365 values, the data dictionary guides researchers to
366 understand and use CDEs correctly.

367 *Figure 11. The community-consent Metadata CDEs and*
368 *Sets of CDEs can be found in the PRECISE-TBI.*
369 *Retrieved October 20, 2025.*

370 In the Data Dictionary (Figure 10), CDE variables are listed under “VariableName”, while the
371 corresponding names in the software program that is used to collect data as “Title”. We have used
372 EthoVison and AHCODA-DB for the data collection and processing. Under the PRECISE-TBI
373 CDE Core website <https://www.precise-tbi.org/common-data-elements> (Figure11) PRECISE-TBI
374 | Common Data Elements (CDEs), users should be able to find Metadata CDEs and sets of CDEs
375 (Xref. LaPlaca, Harris, et al. PRECISE-TBI CDE article). We have identified the CDEs relevant
376 to our study using the existing CDE template. This involves matching the “VariableName”, which
377 corresponds to a CDE data types, and permissible values. Ensure that the data collected aligns with
378 the definitions and standards set by the CDEs (Figure 11). We also need to validate the mapping
379 by checking for consistency and completeness and to document the mapping process thoroughly,
380 including any decisions made and any discrepancies found.

381 After preparing the datasets, metadata dictionary, and description, those files were uploaded to
382 the ODC-TBI repository.

383 To avoid having to map collected variables to CDEs, researchers could follow the PRECISE-
384 TBI recommended CDEs (RRID:SCR_021736; <https://www.precise-tbi.org/cdes>) to format and
385 collect their metadata and data (LaPlaca et al. 2021)(Xref La Placa, Harris, et al. PRECISE-TBI
386 CDE article). A well-defined metadata dictionary with the community-consent CDEs saves time
387 and resources by providing predefined data collection tools. Researchers do not need to create new
388 data definitions from scratch, streamlining the research process.

389 According to the [PRECISE-TBI | Common Data Elements \(CDEs\)](https://www.precise-tbi.org/common-data-elements), a minimal set of variables
390 should be acquired and provided for all preclinical datasets, including unique Subject_ID; Species;
391 Strain; Animal_origin; Age; Weight; Sex; Group, LaboratoryPI name; StudyLeader;
392 Cause_of_Death; Injury_type; Injury_device; Injury_level; Injury_details, Injury Model type,

393 Injury repletion; outcome measure type; outcome measure time; group size range; gene
394 modification; intervention type; GUID etc. As described in the companion article, the ODC-TBI
395 performs checks on each submitted dataset for a subset of these core CDEs (Martone, Ferguson et
396 al., ODC-TBI DMS this issue).

397 Sharing your data on the ODC-TBI platform increases its visibility within the research
398 community, potentially leading to more citations and collaborations (Xref Martone, Ferguson et
399 al., ODC-TBI DMS this issue). The platform helps you comply with the NIH Data Management
400 and Sharing Policy, which requires that scientific data be shared and made accessible. Mapping
401 your data to CDEs and using the data dictionary, it ensures that your data is standardized.

402 As open accessible datasets become increasingly required by the scientific community, ODC-
403 TBI provides a foundation that creates new scientific opportunities for researchers and their work,
404 facilitates multi-dataset and multidimensional analytics, and drives collaboration across molecular
405 and computational biologists to bridge preclinical research to the clinic (Chou et al. 2022; Huie et
406 al. 2021). Furthermore, datasets in Tidy data CSV format make it easy to analyze and manipulate
407 using data analysis tools, particularly within the R programming language and the Tidyverse
408 packages designed for data science and data visualization.

409

410 Use Case: Creating the Paper of the Future from a Graduate 411 Student's Experience

412 The above examples in OFB showcase how the use of PRECISE-TBI tools and
413 recommendations can enrich a publication to make it more transparent, rigorous and reproducible.
414 A question may arise as to the effort required to produce this enriched environment, and so we
415 provide a detailed accounting of a graduate student's experience with using PRECISE-TBI tools
416 prospectively to create a PoF as a first-time user. This use case for the "Paper of the Future" centers
417 on a study of TBI utilizing a rat model of closed-head controlled impact (Talty, Murphy, and
418 VandeVord 2024). This paper discusses the development of depression-like behavior and
419 associated changes in glutamate signaling proteins following TBI. To support efforts to increase
420 standardization, transparency and reproducibility of neurotrauma research, the resources
421 developed by PRECISE-TBI were used to link relevant research objects in this manuscript (Table
422 1). Specifically, this involved the publication of the preclinical TBI protocol on protocols.io,
423 utilization of RRIDs throughout the manuscript to identify key research resources used to produce
424 the findings of our study (Bandrowski and Martone 2016), and submission of subject level to the
425 ODC-TBI repository, with metadata mapped to established CDEs (Bandrowski et al. 2016). A
426 visualization of the connections between the research objects created for this manuscript can be
427 seen in Figure 12.

428 **Creating & Publishing a Protocol Using Protocols.io**

429 A closed-head controlled impact model of TBI was used in this study to measure the
430 subsequent behavioral and pathophysiological outcomes. This method was developed in the
431 Traumatic Nerve Technologies Lab (VandeVord Lab) at Virginia Tech to model closed-head TBI
432 in adult rats. First, the protocol was drafted and reviewed internally by the PI and other lab
433 members before being sent to the team at PRECISE-TBI for review. Through this review process,
434 RRIDs were added for materials in the protocol, including the impactor control box and the
435 electromagnetic actuator. RRIDs are unique identifiers assigned to resources used in research such
436 as antibodies, tools, software, cell lines, and organisms. Including these identifiers alongside
437 descriptions of research materials allows researchers to easily find papers or protocols that utilized
438 any specific material by standardizing reporting practices. After a final review by the PRECISE-
439 TBI team, the protocol was published on protocols.io with a unique DOI. Publication of protocols
440 not only enhances rigor and reproducibility of research studies, but also serves as official
441 documentation of our laboratory’s standard operating procedures and allows for our procedures to
442 be properly credited in future manuscripts. As of the writing of this manuscript, our protocol has
443 been viewed over 200 times in the first year.

444 *Table 1. Linked research products resulting from Paper of the Future*

Product	DOI
Manuscript published in Neuroscience, entitled “Mild traumatic brain injury gives rise to chronic depression-like behavior and associated alterations in glutamatergic protein expression”	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroscience.2024.09.039
Closed-Head Controlled Impact Protocol	https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.dm6gp37z8vzp/v1
Dataset published on ODC-TBI repository, entitled “Mild TBI gives rise to chronic depression-like behavior and associated alterations in glutamatergic protein expression in male Sprague Dawley rats”	https://doi.org/10.34945/F5601T

446

447 *Figure 12. Trainee Use Case for Paper of the Future.*

448

449 Resource Citation Using RRIDs

450 After completing a draft of my manuscript, I went back through the document to insert RRIDs
 451 wherever possible. With the assistance of the PRECISE-TBI team, I was able to determine which
 452 materials had existing RRIDs and which needed RRIDs to be created in the RRID Portal. RRIDs
 453 were inserted for all software, antibodies, reagents and equipment used in the study to promote
 454 ease of reproducibility of the study. The landing page for one of the antibodies used in the study
 455 is shown in Figure 13.

Resource Summary Report

New Search

Previous Search Results

Home / Resource Reports / Antibodies / Resource Summary Report

Antibody Name

*NOTICE: Multiple vendors found, please select your record: Sigma-Aldrich - G8913

Anti-Glutamate Receptor NMDAR1 (NR1) antibody produced in rabbit

RRID:AB_259978

PDF REPORT HOW TO CITE

Antibody Information

URL: http://antibodyregistry.org/AB_259978

Proper Citation: (Sigma-Aldrich Cat# G8913, RRID:AB_259978)

Target Antigen: Glutamate Receptor NMDAR1 (NR1)

Host Organism: rabbit

Clonality: unknown

Comments: Vendor recommendations: Western Blot, Immunoblotting

Expand All

Usage and Citation Metrics

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Liang Q, et al. (2024) NMDAR-CaMKII Pathway as a Central Regulator of Aggressiveness: Evidence from Transcriptomic and Metabolomic Analysis in Swimming Crabs *Portunus trituberculatus*. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 25(23). (PMID: 39684272)Dharmasri PA, et al. (2024) Loss of postsynaptic NMDARs drives nanoscale reorganization of Munc13-1 and PSD-95. *bioRxiv: the preprint server for biology*. (PMID: 38260705)Li L, et al. (2023) *Tiam1* coordinates synaptic structural and functional plasticity underpinning the pathophysiology of neuropathic pain. *Neuron*, 111(13), 2038. (PMID: 37146610)Check [Google Scholar](#) for all resource mentions.

Collaborator Network

A list of researchers who have used the resource and an author search tool

Find mentions based on location

City

Search

[Q Search using your location](#)

456

457 *Figure 13. RRID portal landing page for GluN1 antibody. The red box highlights other*
458 *publications that have used this antibody.*

459 Preparing Metadata and Data for Upload into ODC-TBI

460 All of the data and metadata underlying the results presented in the manuscript were deposited
461 in the ODC-TBI repository, resulting in a dataset publication with a unique DOI. Within the ODC-
462 TBI repository, I was able to “join” our laboratory’s workspace (Martone, Ferguson et al., ODC-
463 TBI DMS this issue), where all datasets from our research group are housed. With the help of a
464 former student from the laboratory (Dr. Carly Norris), we developed a general data dictionary for
465 the lab. This data dictionary serves as a template that may be added to and/or edited to encompass
466 the types of data included in each manuscript that comes out of our lab. Creation of this template
467 was quick and simple because the vast majority of the variables were mapped to the CDEs designed
468 by PRECISE-TBI. From there, I tailored this data dictionary to the types of data present in my
469 Paper of the Future, using the existing CDEs wherever possible, and creating variable names where
470 CDEs did not yet exist.

471 Once I had the data dictionary finalized with all relevant variables, I transposed the variable
472 names into columns in a new spreadsheet and started filling in information for each animal. It is
473 worth noting that a majority of the values for these variables were identical for all animals (i.e.,
474 species, strain, genetic modifications, etc.), making this process quick and painless. Inserting the
475 values for the actual experimental outcomes of the manuscript, such as behavioral and molecular
476 data, was the more tedious part of the process. However, since I had already completed the
477 statistical analysis for these behavioral and molecular datasets in order to write the manuscript, I

478 simply copied and pasted the values right from the statistical software. This was especially
479 convenient because the data was already in order of animal ID. I made note of any outliers in the
480 datasets and for which variables these animals were considered outliers, then the dataset was ready
481 to upload to ODC-TBI.

482 The process of uploading the dataset and its respective data dictionary to the ODC-TBI
483 repository was remarkably smooth. I initially uploaded these documents, then had to make some
484 changes to each as I analyzed the data, requiring me to reupload multiple times but there were no
485 issues making these updates. It was at this point that I added a dataset abstract and description to
486 be paired with the dataset as a summary. Once I had finalized and uploaded all of the dataset
487 materials, I attended an office hours session with the PRECISE-TBI team to have the materials
488 checked over. Following this, I implemented the suggested changes and the PI (Dr. Pamela
489 VandeVord) submitted the dataset for DOI publication. The PRECISE-TBI team reviewed the
490 submitted materials and subsequently provided suggested revisions to the dataset. When the
491 revisions were complete, the dataset was accepted for publication and assigned a unique DOI. A
492 helpful feature of the ODC-TBI repository was the option to hold off on making the dataset and
493 DOI public until the publication date of our manuscript. Therefore, it is beneficial to begin the
494 process of uploading data as soon as you know what data will be included in your manuscript to
495 allow time for dataset review and acceptance so that the dataset DOI can be ready to go for when
496 your Paper of the Future is published.

497

498

499 *Figure 14. Network effect of PoF supports data integration across studies and research groups.*

500 **Reflections**

501 As I reflect on my experience navigating the process of preparing a Paper of the Future, there
 502 are several main takeaways. First and foremost, being proactive when conducting research and
 503 ensuring meticulous organization of data as it is collected are incredibly important practices.
 504 Subject-specific data organization is key to making your ODC-TBI upload as smooth as it can be.
 505 Researchers must have clear records pertaining to all of the values for each group in a given
 506 measure and additionally, must be able to identify which value corresponds to which animal.
 507 Having this information at your fingertips when you go to submit your dataset to the ODC-TBI
 508 repository is vital and keeping this information organized in excel sheets or statistical software for
 509 easy access throughout data collection and analysis is key. Similarly, being proactive in terms of
 510 starting the process of uploading and submitting datasets to the repository well before the
 511 publication of the corresponding manuscript is greatly beneficial so as to allow time for review
 512 and editing of the dataset. Starting this process early decreases the chances that researchers will be
 513 held up waiting for a dataset DOI when it comes time to publish their paper. Integration of RRID
 514 insertion throughout the writing process is also a beneficial practice to adopt when drafting
 515 manuscripts. Now, when I add catalog numbers for resources and materials into my manuscripts,
 516 I also go through my paper to insert RRIDs where they are needed.

517 Overall, turning my manuscript into a Paper of the Future was not nearly as time-intensive or
518 difficult as I had anticipated it would be. The total time that went into this process on my part was
519 on the order of days, not weeks or months, and it has only gotten quicker each time I have gone
520 through the process. There was a bit of a learning curve for me as far as learning about tidy format
521 and data dictionaries, but now preparing my data is a breeze. It is also convenient that publication
522 of laboratory protocols is something that only needs to be completed once, requiring some effort
523 for the first Paper of the Future being published, but not those that come after. For example, several
524 of our research group’s protocols have now been published, so all we need to do going forward is
525 cite them. While the first time a researcher writes a Paper of the Future may be a learning
526 experience, this process gets exponentially easier with each paper and eventually becomes the
527 “new normal” for preparing manuscripts.

528 **Conclusions**

529 Peer-reviewed journals emphasize the importance of rigorous methodologies and
530 reproducibility in research, yet these can be challenging without standardized data practices.
531 PRECISE-TBI supports and enhances traditional publication by providing tools for planning,
532 conducting and sharing research outcomes. Through these tools, the research paper becomes only
533 one of the research products published. By publishing the protocol as a separate yet linked research
534 object using the protocols.io platform, we avoid journal space limitations on the methods and
535 can therefore provide as much detail as needed. Similarly, rather than publishing summaries of
536 data and statistical outcomes only, the individual subject level data can be published. This
537 approach showcases a “paper of the future” in preclinical TBI studies. The ODC-TBI repository
538 provides a user-centered web platform and cloud-based ecosystem on preclinical TBI research. It
539 promotes data element harmonization by encouraging the use of PRECISE CDEs, enabling
540 researchers to use a common framework for data collection and analysis. Using CDEs, the data
541 collected from individual labs is compatible with other datasets, fostering collaboration and
542 sharing across different studies and organizations.

543 The concept of the Paper of the Future is beneficial not only because it supports efforts to
544 increase standardization, transparency and reproducibility of neurotrauma research, but it is also
545 beneficial to investigators and research groups. Publication of protocols on protocols.io allows for
546 laboratory protocols to be conveniently stored and accessible in one place for the use of the
547 researchers and are not subject to word limitations of research articles. Furthermore, the
548 laboratories that developed these protocols can be properly cited when other researchers use their
549 methodologies. Preparation of datasets for upload to the ODC-TBI repository encourages
550 standardization of data organization within laboratories, which will make it easier to find data from
551 former lab members or older research projects in the future. When each investigator has their own
552 unique way of organizing their data, it can sometimes be difficult to decipher the logic by which
553 data has been organized. Transformation of project datasets into tidy format allows for quick and
554 efficient location of important metadata. Additionally, publication of datasets on ODC-TBI makes
555 it possible for other research groups to use your data for different analyses to build upon our

556 understanding of TBI outcomes. The unique DOI assigned to each dataset allows your dataset to
557 be cited when it is used by others, ensuring proper attribution. The research elements developed
558 for a “Paper of the Future” become linked not only to the manuscript itself, but to other studies
559 which utilized the same protocol, RRIDs, and datasets mapped to the same CDEs ultimately
560 creating a network effect among preclinical neurotrauma publications (Figure 14).

561 **Remarks.** The PRECISE-TBI consortium, through the established and ongoing development
562 of toolkits and resources, enables to assist and promote open sharing of comprehensive preclinical
563 TBI datasets generated by multiple labs within the TBI research community. The goal is to make
564 these datasets publicly available to encourage FAIR data reuse. By leveraging the power of AI and
565 data science advancements, we aim to enhance rigor and reproducibility, maximizing the value of
566 these datasets and amplifying the public investment in preclinical TBI research. As the National
567 Institutes of Health is expanding its view of model systems for translational research through its
568 new policy on the use of animals in research, PRECISE resources can also become important tools
569 for researchers to utilize alongside the more traditional animal-based paradigms.

570 **Graphic Abstract.** Illustrative summary for the Paper of the Future using the OFB studies as a
571 ‘Use Case’.

572

573 *Figure 15. shows the results of utilizing the PRECISE-TBI tools. The original papers have now been*
574 *enriched with an array of resources that increase transparency, rigor and reproducibility. All are*
575 *published as independent objects which can be used and cited independently, but all are linked together so*
576 *that the complete package of research objects associated with this dataset can be easily retrieved from open*
577 *platforms. The above examples show that even if a paper is published already, with good data management*
578 *and research documentation in the lab, the paper can be “retrofitted” with these products.*

580 **References:** Cite relevant literature.

581

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